

Neutrino echoes \Rightarrow late light produced $> 1 \mu\text{s}$ after Cherenkov emission from neutrino interaction

This optical echo occurs due to Michel electrons, neutron captures and nuclear effects in ice producing subdominant photon peaks

This info could help **NCxCC discrimination** in the IceCube Upgrade

Daemonflux + nuSQuIDS + GENIEv3 used for In ice neutrino generation
Secondary Particles propagated in GEANT4, using Thermal corrections and PYTHIA8 for tau decay

Methodology

Importance Sampling

Timing Distributions

Boosted Decision Tree

Takeaway

IceCube Upgrade \Rightarrow ~ 700 new sensors in **heart of IceCube** capable of detecting neutron echos deployed now!

We expect $O(10 \text{ MHz})$ selected neutrino events in Upgrade, and $O(1000)$ echoes per year

Late timing information may help to distinguish CC from NC neutrinos - important for oscillation analyses!